
METHODS OF RESOLVING ISSUES FORMING ECONOMIC RELATIONS

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Abstract.

Mathematics is such a science that it is inextricably linked with every field. That is why the connection with economic sectors plays an incomparable role in the development of our society. Teaching this to students is finding its high place in the development of analytical thinking and the formation of thrift in the family.

Key words.

analytical thinking, interpretation, analysis, thinking based on logic and evidence, evaluation, explanation, verification, thrift, creative development, striving for perfection, underground and surface resources, logical thinking.

Analytical thinking is independent thinking. Each person's thinking is individual and different from others. And information is the starting point of analytical thinking. In methodological literature published by Western scientists, the following features are included as parameters affecting the method of imparting knowledge:

- individual characteristics of each student;
- ability to process and analyze information;
- students to interact and cooperate with each other.

We can learn from these theories of knowledge that children's correct analysis of each example and problem serves as the basis for 70% correct results in solving them. There are six tools of thinking associated with analytical thinking. They are as follows:

Interpretation

Interpretation is the ability to correctly understand the information presented to you and convey it to others. In this case, students are required to be able to understand the meaning of the condition of the given example or problem and be able to share it with their partners.

Analysis

Analysis is the process of summarizing information from various parts and understanding their conclusion. . In this case, students are required to correctly place the numbers and numerical data in the conditions of the given example or problem.

3- Thinking based on logic and evidence

Logical and evidence-based thinking is understood as the ability to choose a convenient method of a problem or example in order to reach the correct conclusion or result based on available information. That is, in order to correctly find the requested information while solving a problem, it is necessary to apply the action that needs to be found before it and achieve the result. Let's see this with a problem:

"Issue 4

There were 14 boys and 16 girls in the room when 22 children left the room, and the number of boys and girls became equal. How many boys left the room?"

Given: 14 boys

There are 16 girls

22 people left

To find: the number of boys who left the room.

To solve this problem correctly, we must first find the total number of children in the room. Then we can find the number of children left in the room by subtracting the number of students who left from the number of all children. we can find the number and subtract the number of boys in the room from the total number of boys to find the number of boys who left. Here, understanding the number of boys and girls in the room from the condition of the problem and finding the right solution to the problem can be an example of thinking based on logical arguments.

Evaluation

During assessment, students believe that information is being used correctly and that they are not being confused with one another.

you need to be able to correctly assess the impartiality of the decision.

Explanation

This is one of the basic laws that are needed and required of more teachers. The problem is that it is important not only to convey the information in the examples, but also to know how to explain it with additional information. Because you need to be able to answer the additional questions of the person receiving the

information from you. When you learn something, you need to know enough to explain it to others. So, you should always be ready to fully explain the topic of case studies.

6- Check

During this process, it is necessary to check and study the correctness of the result obtained from the worked example or problem. If some errors and omissions were made during the solution of the problem, how else can the problem be solved? Where are the mistakes made? It is necessary to try to find answers to such questions.

"Has the foundations of economic theory to master economic principles (as a 'guide to action') and learn to make competent decisions; the surrounding world, modern clearly understands the economic realities of the time, regularly replenishes knowledge in order to "keep up to date"; builds a strategy of his economic behavior based on economic principles; learns the main models of economic behavior and economic roles; has modern economic thinking; increases independent decision-making skills; speaks economic language, which allows you to clearly express your opinion; has business, oral and written communication skills; owns the main elements of economic culture: activity, behavior, communicative, value; he respects his own and other people's property, his own and other people's work, and is proud of his economic achievements."

Taking into account the age characteristics of students, I have highlighted several directions that should be paid attention to when working with primary school students.

1. What is money?
2. What is the price?
3. Income and expenses of the family.
4. We go to the store.
5. We spend money at school.
6. In the school cafeteria.

Preparation - in the 1st grade, a lot of role-playing games were given: "Store", "Post Office", etc. In the family income and expenses lesson, students are divided into 4 groups - forest families: "Hedgehogs", "Rabbits", "Badgers", "Wolves". We will distribute the problems of suitable food products and teach how to solve them and how much they will spend in their families.

Issues:

1. For Tipratikans family. Tipratikan father buys apples and pears for his family every Sunday. He buys 12 apples and 7 pears for each of his 4 children, himself and their mother. If the price of each apple is 50 soums and each pear is 40 soums, how much does the hedgehog spend for his family in one week? How about 2 weeks?

Given: 6 hedgehogs

12 apples each

7 pears each

One apple is 50 soums

One pear is 40 soums

Solution: 1) $6 \times 12 = 72$ apples

2) $6 \times 7 = 42$ pears

3) Apple $72 \times 50 = 3600$ soums

4) $42 \times 40 = 1680$ soums pears

5) $3600 + 1680 = 5280$ soums

Answer: it costs 5280 soums per week

Now we need to multiply the result by 2 to find how much it will cost for 2 weeks. Then the cost of 2 weeks will arise.

Solution: 1) $5280 \times 2 = 10560$ soums.

Answer: 10,560 soums.

2. For the rabbit family. Mother Rabbit buys carrots, cabbage and beets for her family every Sunday. He buys 7 carrots, 8 cabbages and 9 beets for each of his 5 children, himself and his children's grandmother. If the price of each carrot is 50 soums, and each cabbage costs 40 soums, and each beetroot costs 30 soums, how much will the rabbits cost for their family in a week? How about 2 weeks?

Given: the total number of rabbits is 7

7 carrots each

8 cabbages for each

9 beets each

One carrot is 50 soums

One cabbage is 40 soums

One beet is 30 soums

Solution:

1) $7 \times 7 = 49$ carrots

2) $7 \times 8 = 56$ cabbages

3) $7 \times 9 = 63$ beets

- 4) $49 \times 50 = 2450$ soums
- 5) $56 \times 40 = 2240$ soums
- 6) $63 \times 30 = 1890$ soums
- 7) $2450 + 2240 + 1890 = 6580$ soums

Answer: they spend 6580 soums in one week.

To find out how much he spent in 1 week, we multiply the cost for one week by 2.

Solution: 1) $6580 \times 2 = 13160$ soums

The answer is 13160 soums for 2 weeks.

Thrift is the ability to constantly develop oneself physically, spiritually, mentally, intellectually and creatively, to strive for perfection, to learn independently throughout one's life, and to make independent decisions. By forming thriftiness in children, they develop the ability to feel connected to the events, events and processes taking place in society and actively participate in them, to know their civil duties and rights before people in society, to comply with them, and to acquire human culture. It is an economic attitude towards economical use of all resources at a certain level of social and economic development of society and is the main factor of ensuring production efficiency. Indeed, people have been wasting a lot of things these days. That is why we have lost almost a third of our wealth on earth. Therefore, whenever we have the opportunity, we need to protect the earth and protect it. We should inculcate these things in the minds of our children from a young age, teach them that everything will end one day, and the need to protect them all the time. For this, first of all, it is necessary for us adults to be a role model for them, to give them every blessing. Because the earth is a universe with humanity, animals and plants. Scientists say that if humanity does not stop waste sooner, our planet will have more as it gets lost and disappears. If we use the above-ground and underground resources of our planet in the right way, without waste, our spiritual and material resources will last for many years and will be passed on to the next generation.

We can understand the inextricable aspects of the formation of thriftiness with the science of mathematics through the following problem.

Issue 2

The price of 1 egg in the store is 10 soums. If customers buy more than 10 eggs from the store, 2 eggs will be added for each additional 5 eggs purchased. Nigora's family has 8 people and she buys 20 eggs every week. How many extra eggs does

Nigora get for the eggs she gets, and how many soums does she save for her family?

The condition of this problem forces children to think logically, and as a result of finding a solution, they are taught how to benefit the family budget. This, in turn, serves as a basis for preparing children for the future life.

Including many issues of this content in the textbooks will help to further increase the economic education of children and the formation of thrift qualities.

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